

UNVEILING THE FINANCIAL CHALLENGES FACED BY TEACHERS IN NORTH PRESIDENT QUIRINO DISTRICT

Baby Sydney L. Nasi

*Teacher III, Lamasan Elementary School, President Quirino North District
Division of Sultan Kudarat*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701299>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to explore and gain an in-depth understanding of the financial challenges experienced by teachers, including factors that contribute to financial stress and potential strategies for improving their financial wellness. This research used qualitative research which is a research approach that allows the researcher to interpret the life of people to understand their problems better and deeper to generate solutions that are relevant to their situations. The participants of the study are 10 teachers from North President Quirino District for the school year 2023-2024. A semi-structured guide questionnaire was used and thematic analysis was employed to generate themes. On the financial challenges faced by the teachers, the following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants of the study such as Education Related, Health Related, and Home Needs Related. The financial challenges they encountered affected their family, profession, and school-work-related orientation, the following themes were generated based on the shared responses of the study, Increased Stress, and Create Tensions and Arguments. Interestingly, themes were generated based on the responses of the participants, Positive Mindset and Financial Management, Seeking Advice and Comfort, and Trust in the Lord. A similar study shall be undertaken utilizing the same instrument and methodologies but in different settings and bigger samples.

Keywords: *Financial Challenges, Teachers, Coping Mechanism, North President Quirino, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Financial well-being is directly related to the overall satisfaction a person feels regarding his financial status. Financial wellness is an active state of financial health evidenced by low debt levels, active savings and retirement plans, and a good spending plan. Low financial well-being or the presence of financial distress is shown to have detrimental effects on psychological and physical health, reduced confidence and productivity in the workplace, and increased absenteeism, delays, as well as lack of concentration. Hence, the financial condition of teachers is a contributory factor for effective and quality education

Financial literacy focuses on the ability to manage personal finance matters efficiently including the knowledge of making appropriate decisions about personal finance, such as investing, insurance, real estate, paying for college, budgeting, retirement, and tax planning (Kenton, 2019).

Financial literates can answer several questions about purchases, such as whether an item is required, whether it is affordable, and whether it is an asset or a liability. Financial literacy therefore shows how an individual makes financial decisions and helps a person develop a financial road map to identify what he earns, what he spends, and what he owes. The Department of Education (2017) through Secretary Leonor Briones highlighted that financial literacy is crucial for teachers, especially because the teachers' debt has been increasing.

Hence, the Education Chief highlighted that the agency welcomes financial literacy programs and further said that there is an urgent need to help teachers cope with their finances after it was found out that most teachers have various loans. The lack of financial literacy can lead to owing large amounts of debt and making poor financial decisions. Public school teachers have indebted a combined balance of at least P319 billion, an increase of P18 billion in just over two years.

In a study conducted by Fausto (2019), the teachers' problem is not the amount of salary, but the environment makes it so easy, if not attractive, to take on loans. They just need to show their pay slip and they instantly get a loan. Even the GSIS and PFIs make it so easy for them to make a loan, and some even give freebies. Even the teachers who have not yet received their first salary can already avail of a loan.

Henceforth, the solution is not just a salary increase, nor making more loans available to them, but it became very clear that the principles of Behavioral Economics may be used to solve this problem – both in the policies and in helping the teachers individually. But on the teachers' side, they claim that they are not big spenders as they feel they may be perceived when this problem is tackled. They resist Financial Literacy as a solution.

Hence, this study is conceived to unveil the financial challenges and financial status of teachers in North President Quirino District.

Research Questions

The study focuses on the financial challenges faced by teachers in North President Quirino District. Specifically, the study was carried out with the following research objectives;

1. Determined the financial challenges faced by the teachers.
2. Describe how these financial challenges they encountered affect their family, profession, and school work-related orientation.
3. Narrate their coping mechanism to address those challenges they experienced.

METHODOLOGY

The study uses qualitative research, particularly phenomenology research design that interprets the life of people to understand their problems better and deeper to generate solutions that are relevant to their situations.

A Semi-structured guide survey questionnaire was used to collect the necessary information and responses from the participants of the study.

The participants of the study were ten (10) teachers regardless of the plantilla position for the school year 2023-2024

RESULTS

On the financial challenges faced by the teachers, the following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants of the study such as Education Related, Health Related, and Home Needs Related.

The financial challenges they encountered affected their family, profession, and school-work-related orientation, the following themes were generated based on the shared responses of the study, Increased Stress, and Create Tensions and Arguments

Interestingly, themes were generated based on the responses of the participants, Positive Mindset and Financial Management, Seeking Advice and Comfort, and Trust in the Lord.

DISCUSSION

On the financial challenges faced by the teachers, the following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants of the study such as Education Related, Health Related, and Home Needs Related.

The first theme that was generated was education-related. As the participants share the financial challenges faced by the teachers;

“As a teacher, I am financially challenged because I have two college students studying I am supporting their expenses, household expenses, and personal expenses resorted me to debts or loans because my monthly salary could not suffice on our monthly expenses”. **Participant 2, Teacher III, Female**

Another participant shared their experiences on the challenges that they had faced;

“I am financially challenged every time monthly dues are waived. The tuition fees of my child, nieces, and nephews, as well as the current tuition fee of my graduate schooling. The monthly amortization of our transport vehicle. I was also challenged financially in times of emergency for our family”. **Participant 4, Teacher III, Female;**

The second theme that was generated was **education-related challenges**. As the participants shared;

“I was financially challenged when one of the members of my family rushed up to the hospital. I also considered the school expenses of my children”. **Participant 3, Teacher III, Female;**

“I am financially challenged with my husband’s medication and during his burial”. **Participant 8, Master Teacher I, Female**

The last theme that was generated in the responses of the participants was the **Home Needs Related**. As the participants openly share their experiences;

“My husband and I have two children and we are both government employees. Managing my finances has been one of the challenges of my life. It seems to be a big challenge for me to budget our salary for food, home bills, and other stuff”. **Participant 5, Teacher III, Female;, and**

“As a teacher, sometimes I am also financially challenged for I am now building my home in preparation for my retirement, and I am the sole provider for our family because I have been a widow for some years”. **Participant 9, Master Teacher I, Female**

On the financial challenges they encountered affected their family, profession, and school-work-related orientation the following themes were generated based on the shared responses of the study, a. **Increased Stress and Create Tensions and Arguments**

The first theme was **increased stress**; as the participants shared their views on this topic;

“Financial challenges, such as low salaries or other difficulties, can affect my family because it can lead to increased stress and strain. Trying to make ends meet, pay bills, and cover educational expenses can take a toll on the emotional well-being of myself, my husband, and my children.” **Participant 1, Teacher III, Female;**

“My family was affected because of being financially unstable and feeling stressed. The budget for household expenses will be reduced.”

Participant 3, Teacher III, Female;

“Economic hardship and financial distress can have devastating effects on families. In tough economic times, many families lose their jobs, homes, cars, retirement accounts, belongings, savings health, insurance, and more. Families often struggle just to meet their basic needs.”

Participant 7, Master Teacher I, Female

The last theme generated was, **Create Tensions and Arguments**, as the participants shared their thoughts in this matter.

“It can create tensions and arguments among family members as we have different opinions on how to handle it.” **Participant 4, Teacher III, Female**

“Financial Problems make me stressed, sometimes it can cause conflict and reduce the overall happiness of my family.” **Participant 5, Teacher III, Female**

“Economic hardship and financial distress can have devastating effects on families. In tough economic times, many families lose their jobs, homes, cars, retirement accounts, belongings, savings health, insurance, and more. Families often struggle just to meet their basic needs.”

Participant 7, Master Teacher I, Female

The following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants, **a. Positive Mindset and Financial Management and b. Seeking Advice and Comfort and Trust in the Lord** on their coping mechanisms

The first theme that was generated was a positive mindset and financial management.

With this, financial management is all about monitoring, controlling, protecting, and reporting on a company's financial resources. The participants shared their coping strategies as;

“Maintaining a positive mindset and focusing on the impact I can have on my pupils’ lives has been crucial in coping with financial challenges. By staying resilient and dedicated to my pupil’s success, I have been able to navigate the obstacles and continue delivering a high-quality education, despite financial constraints. Lastly, by being resourceful, proactive, and maintaining a positive outlook in life. I have been able to cope with the financial challenges and continue to provide education for my pupils.”

Participant 1, Teacher III, Female;

“Continuing to be tenacious and committed both to my students’ education and my teaching is one of my inspirations to work more, have a more optimistic attitude, and concentrate on my teaching is one of my coping mechanisms to fight the financial struggles that I encounter in my life.” **Participant 10, Master Teacher, Female;**

“To combat financial problems, make a budget to help resolve financial problems. Lower my expenses, stop taking on debts to avoid aggravating my financial problem.” **Participant 4, Teacher III, Female;**

The second theme that was generated was **Seeking advice and Comfort and Trust in the Lord.**

The participants shared their coping mechanisms as;

“My coping mechanism is to address the challenges I have faced. I opened my financial problem to the people whom I trusted to seek advice and comfort. A gradual change in our lifestyle was done not spending too much during occasions, prioritizing needs, and limiting weekend activities.” **Participant II, Teacher III, Female**

“To cope with those situations, I had to face. I talked and sought advice from the people I trusted most.” **Participant 9, Master Teacher, Female**

“Based on the challenges that we faced as a family, my coping mechanism to address all that I have shared is to turn to God. When I feel so depressed because of all these problems, I fall on my knees and pray to God for giving me the strength to face all these challenges and providing and giving me the strength.” **Participant 6, Master Teacher, Female.**

The findings support Legg's (2020)' assertion that some stressors are unable to be modified or controlled. As a result, solution-focused/problem-focused coping strategies may not be the most effective way to deal with stress. Simple activities such as meditation, taking time for oneself, and talking to oneself can, on the other hand, be powerful stress relievers. The reason for this is that it enables a person to identify inside himself or herself how to transform unfavorable situations into positive ones. This helps to foster positive thinking and optimism, which can help with stress management.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

Education Related, Health Related, Home needs Related are themes that was generated on the financial challenges faced by the teachers. Whereas, Increased Stress, Create Tensions and Arguments affect their family and workplace.

But regardless of those challenges' participants had a Positive Mindset and Financial Management, and Seeking Advice and Comfort and Trust in the Lord.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented;

1. Financial knowledge and financial attitude of teachers may be strengthened through a financial literacy seminar, especially the newly hired teachers.
2. Teachers' salary may be increased to cope with the expenses incurred in their household and increase their net take home pay as well.

3. A similar study shall be undertaken utilizing the same instrument and methodologies but in different settings and bigger samples.
-

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

Acknowledgments

The acknowledgment goes to the participants for their shared time and contribution to the researchers whose work has been referenced in this paper and most especially to Leodie D. Mones, PhD for his technical assistance in completing this paper. Their valuable insights and findings have substantially contributed to the analysis of this study.

REFERENCES

- Fausto, Rose Fres (2019). Teachers' fret: 'Lending na Walang Ending'.
<https://www.philstar.com/lifestyle/healthandfamily/2019/07/17/1935215/teachers-fret-lending-na-walang-ending>
- Kenton, W., 2019. Financial Literacy, <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/financial-literacy.asp>
- Legg T. (2020). Positive Self-Talk: How Talking to Yourself Is a Good Thing